

Strategic Planning and Organizational Performance in Seed Processing Companies in Trans Nzoia County, Kenya

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Abstract: This study is intended to establish the effect of strategic planning on the performance of seed processing companies in TransNzoia County, Kenya. The specific objective of the study was to identify the effect of resource availability on organizational performance in seed processing companies in TransNzoia County. The study is guided by the Resource based theory. The study adopted a descriptive research design with a target population of 89 management staff of the seed companies. Data collection instrument was questionnaire. Piloting was done to test the validity and reliability of the data collection instruments. The data was then be analyzed using SPSS version 26 and presented through tables and graphs. The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics that is a linear regression model for the study. From the findings, resource availability ($\beta = 0.769$) was found to be positively related to organizational performance in seed processing companies in TransNzoia county, Kenya. The study recommends that the management of seed companies should ensure that regular budgeting and reviews in its strategic planning and that resource availability, outcome waste or within minimum use of resources such as energy, finances, labor and time critically in driving the success of any organization. The management of seed companies should come up with regular training programs to equip employees with latest skills, knowledge, and abilities, with the aim of building organizational capabilities and improving organizational performance. The results of the study should be relevant to the management of the seed processing companies within and without TransNzoia County.

Keywords: Strategic Planning, Resource Availability.

1. INTRODUCTION

The concept of strategy is known to have originated from the military with Sun Tzu's 'The Art of War' written around 400BC, Pardo (2017) being the earliest literature on strategies used by the military to defeat the enemy, which involved identifying the type of resource to be used at the most appropriate time to win a war. In the contemporary organization context strategy is the action that managers take to achieve one or more of the organization's goals. Collin White simplifies it as a unifying idea which links purpose and action, White (2017). Alfred D. Chandler defines it as 'the determination of

the basic, long-term goals and objectives of an enterprise, and the adoption of courses of action and the allocation of resources necessary for those goals', Smothers et al (2010). Planning on the other hand is the process of deciding what is to be done in the future, Henry Fayol considers it as one of the five functions of management thus; plan; organize; coordinate; command and control, he defines planning as deciding the best alternative among others to perform different managerial operations in order to achieve the predetermined goals, Pugh and Hickson (2007). Planning therefore precedes all other managerial activities. Strategic planning ensures the survival of a business amidst the competition, it is an organizational management activity that is used to set priorities, focus energy and resources, strengthen operations, ensure that employees and other stakeholders are working toward common goals, establish agreement on intended results, and assess and adjust the organization's direction in response to a changing environment, Mohammadian (2017)

Strategic planning is therefore a part of strategic management, which is the entire process of determining the direction of an organization from planning to execution. A good strategy will certainly be achieved only through a thorough planning process. Changes in approaches to management in both public and private sectors has become necessary as globalization imposes a new challenge. The resultant market dynamics have led to challenges for organizations, with the emergence of the global economy, advances in technology, growing competition, increased consumer demands and awareness. Corporate governance has resulted in greater scrutiny for organizations as stakeholders are more informed in looking after their interest as information and knowledge become more accessible.

Organizational strategic management has grown in prominence in the information age, when the competition can easily replicate an organization's innovations wiping out its competitive advantage, thus the necessity for change is unpredictable, it is often reactive, discontinuous, ad hoc and often triggered by a situation of organizational crisis, Burnes (2004). As Bovaird (2003) argues, an organization lacking a strategy does not have direction and leads to it being incompetent. Strategic management is paramount particularly in this era when there is stiff competition and pressure from stakeholders for example shareholders who demand a good return on their investment, therefore management must do more with less resource input. Response measures have been implemented within the private sector to confront such challenges but government organizations have been slower to respond. This is understandable, given fiscal constraints and the bureaucratic process akin to governments. Public institutions however, need a new approach, which must incorporate modern strategic management tools, for the public sector to achieve improved performance especially on service quality, Mutunga (2017)

The information age spurred by the advent of the internet and mobile communication from the late 20th century has seen the acceleration of globalization and made the world a global village, Williams et al (2013). Strategic management is practiced all over the world and is even more crucial to multinational corporations operating across different continents. Managers in such organizations adopt an agile-infused as opposed to the traditional planning process, Matychak (2005), an agile strategy is one with a philosophy that enables organizations to sustain strategic momentum while frequently deploying and sustaining strategic initiatives. Effective agile strategy processes provide just enough planning to launch executable initiatives early, focusing less on exhaustive long-term planning and more on early execution in the form of action planning, measuring, and re-evaluating approaches as a matter of regular business, Gates (2018).

Resource availability is critical in driving the success of any organization. These resources can be human resources, assets, facilities, equipment, and more. According to Rose et al (2010), resources are both the tangible and intangible assets a firm employs to select and implement its strategies. The availability of each type of resource that is utilized by the organization is necessary for continuity of its operations. According to Burke (2013), available resources are the assets that an organization possesses and can readily access and utilize them in its operations, which include human resources, financial resources, materials and equipment. The study recognizes that although aspects of strategic planning are common to all types of organizations, the utilization of planning processes must be carefully customized to the public sector environment when applied by public sector organizations. More specifically, public managers must accommodate the perspectives and needs of those stakeholders with whom they must cooperate. Over the last two decades, strategic planning in Canadian government institutions has gained importance owing to the increased public demand for both accountability and transparency. Government institutions are required to produce annual reports on plans and priorities by strategic outcomes, program and expected results for a three-year period, playing an important role in the Government's planning and resource management. The study notes some authors' suggestion that excessive attention to the planning process may make decision-making inflexible and thereby inevitably leading to implementation failure as managers are unable to make incremental

adaptations to a plan that is rigid, Obeidat and Udin (2021). Thus emphasizing the need for a flexible and open process of planning and implementation, ensuring that organizations can learn more effectively and respond to environmental changes during strategic plan implementation.

In a study by Aldehayyat, Jehad & Twaissi, Naseem. (2011) titled Strategic Planning and Corporate Performance Relationship in Small Business Firms: Evidence from a Middle East Country Context. The goal of this research was to identify strategic planning system characteristics in Jordanian small industrial firms and to examine its relationship with corporate performance. The authors acknowledged that formal strategic planning is an explicit and continuous organizational process that comprises of a number of components, such as the establishment of goals and the generation and evaluation of strategies (Bergstrom et al, 2013). The formal strategic planning process is analytical, systematic and deliberate. Aldehayyat, Anchor.(2010) Outline the benefits of strategic planning to organizations; enhancing co-ordination between departments; controlling by reviewing performance and progress toward objectives; identifying and exploiting future marketing opportunities; enhancing internal communication between staff; motivating staff to focus on the organization's goals and improving and sustaining organizational performance.

The authors avers that most of the research on the subject has been done only in the US and other developed European countries but little in the Middle East, moreover none were in the scope of small firms. Therefore, this research aims to fill the gap in the literature and provide new empirical evidence about strategic planning characteristics in Jordanian small business firms and to examine their relationship with corporate performance. The research was conducted via a survey of small industrial publicly listed Jordanian firms. The results of the survey provided a rich source of data in relation to a variety of practices associated with strategic planning in small Jordanian industrial firms. The findings provided empirical evidence about the involvement of top and line management in planning, environmental screening, and the use of strategy tools and techniques, functional coverage. Additionally, the study found a strong positive relationship between strategic planning and corporate performance.

Africa's most populous country, Nigeria with 216 Million people and per capita of \$2,097.1 (World Bank National Accounts Data, 2022), is also the largest market per country in the continent. However, organizations in Nigeria must do more than just avail their products to this market to achieve success. In a study by Ikem et al (2016) on Strategic Planning and Organizational Performance: The Nigerian Experience, the authors note that it is possible that an organization having equal capacity in staff, capital and material with another could perform better or poorer than the other organization. The difference can be attributed to managerial effectiveness in response to changes in the environment like consumer tastes and preferences, technological changes, political, social and cultural changes. This will determine how strategically prepared a company is to maintain a competitive position, as supported by Adeleke, Ogundele and Oyenuga, (2008).The paper evaluated the effects of strategic planning on the performance of firms in Nigeria. The need to position companies strategically is what brought about planning as a managerial function and led to organizational strategic planning.

In conclusion therefore, the study finds that strategic planning as crucial as it is to firm's progress possesses very weak positive relationship with organizational performance in Nigeria. This mixed result does not support previous studies such as Oyedijo (2012). Scholars in support of non-formalized strategic planning argue that it has no performance benefit to SMEs thus strategic planning has a tendency to cause rigidity in a business organization which diminishing its adaptability to the dynamic and competitive environment as Vliet (2011) finds from Henry Mintzberg. In contrast advocates of formalized strategic planning indicate that some performance benefits are attributable to strategic planning, Desai (2000.) They claim that strategic planning is a management tool which cushions businesses from unstable and competitive markets. Emily Njoroge (2018) studied on effect of strategic planning on organizational performance of event planning firms in the CBD. The author noted the work of Awino et al (2012) that strategic planning is a backbone support to strategic management and is a major process in the conduct of strategic management. Many organizations today are focusing on becoming more competitive by formulating and implementing competitive strategies that give them an edge over others.

Simerson (2011), highlights some benefits of Strategic planning as: It provides much needed focus and direction to an organization's management, enables an organization to make fundamental decisions about the market in which it will operate, and how to differentiate itself from its competitors, an organization is able to review its progress to date, it helps management to identify strategies and tactics that will help the organization to achieve its objectives, helps the organization to identify the resources necessary to achieve desired results, enables the organization to be proactive that is be prepared

for any outcome, whether desirable or otherwise. There have been some studies on strategic planning, but some were either inconclusive on the factors affecting this process or contradictory on the impact of strategic planning on business performance. Studies on the subject by Mutunga (2017) focused on one entity, the health department of Nairobi County, while Njoroge (2018) narrowed down to start ups in the CBD of Nairobi city, furthermore, they do not capture the challenges of strategic planning amidst competition, specifically effect of risks, skills and stakeholder participation. Moreover, there are limited studies capturing the unique context of strategic planning in seed processors in TransNzoia County. Therefore, the study seeks to analyze the effect of strategic planning on organizational performance in seed processing companies in TransNzoia County, Kenya. The specific objective identify the effect of resource availability on organizational performance in seed processing companies in TransNzoia County, Kenya.

2. RESOURCE AVAILABILITY AND ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE

Resource availability is critical in driving the success of any organization. These resources can be human resources, assets, facilities, equipment, and more. According to Rose et al (2010), resources are both the tangible and intangible assets a firm employs to select and implement its strategies. The availability of each type of resource that is utilized by the organization is necessary for continuity of its operations. According to Burke (2013), available resources are the assets that an organization possesses and can readily access and utilize them in its operations, which include human resources, financial resources, materials and equipment. The availability of the requisite resources for a firm is subject to its management. The organization's management must therefore carry out resource management, which is the process of utilizing various types of business resources efficiently and effectively. It refers to the planning, scheduling, and future allocation of resources to the right purpose at the right time and cost. While a good strategy, an adequate and effective pool of skills in the human capital are extremely important resources for strategy success, poor leadership in the utilization of resources is one of the main obstacles in successful strategy implementation, leading to failed organizations, Cater and Pucko (2010).

Ismail et al (2012) examined the relationship between organizational resources, capabilities, systems and competitive advantage in terms of value and quantity and found that there is significant, positive effects of organizational resources, capabilities and systems collectively on competitive advantage. Barney (2007) claims that competitive advantage will lead to superior performance, given the fact that many firms focus their competitive strategy towards securing their resource pool. Additionally, Barnes (2007) suggests that an organization's resources which may include capabilities, organizational processes, the firms attributes, is information and knowledge that is owned and controlled by the organization which will eventually enable the firm to conceive and implement strategies that will maximize its efficiency and effectiveness, giving it superior performance over its competitors. The right managers for any firm results in effective decision making, In order to enhance organizational effectiveness, senior management strive for better leadership, communication, adaptability, interaction and a positive environment for employees to improve organization's effectiveness. Organizational effectiveness is defined as the proficiency with which a firm can meet its objectives by meeting the planned outcome without waste or within minimum use of resources such as energy, finances, labor and time, (Lunenburg 2012).

Organizational effectiveness can also be viewed as the extent to which an organization's main tasks are accomplished with the construct of effectiveness being compactly associated with successful organization performance. To measure effectiveness, Lee and Choi, (2003) proposed a criterion that includes overall success, market share, profitability, growth rate and innovation. Commonly used measures of organizational effectiveness for a firm are net profitability outcome compared to planned or expected profitability, growth achieved over a given period, and customer satisfaction measured by repeat purchases. Efficiency on the other hand refers to the amount of resources, such as raw materials, labor, and cash, used to achieve a certain outcome in an organization, the higher the ratio of output to the value of the inputs, the higher the efficiency, (Lee and Choi, 2003).

Differences in performance of organizations operating in the same industry can be attributed to the level of resources they possess, Tokuda , (2005), the resources under the control of a firm generally enhance its performance, however, some firms possess vast resources yet this does not reflect in its performance. Inefficient leadership causes a reduction in the finances that investors are willing to inject in a firm which in turn negatively affects the potential performance of that organization, (Lunenburg 2012). Rajasekar,(2014) notes that human resources management plays an important role in the effective implementation of strategic plans. GoK (2013) indicate that weak human resources and institutional capacity to attract and retain the skills needed to drive performance, has characterized many state corporations to the level that they require support

from the exchequer. The relationship between organizational resources and firm performance has been the subject of many studies and there is evidence that organizational resources have an impact on organizational performance, (Lunenburg, 2012). Barney (2007) claims that intangible resources are more sustainable than tangible resources which are susceptible to acquisition or duplication by the firm's competitors. A firm's superior performance is as a result of a combination of resources that are both tangible and intangible. Baker and Sinkula (2009) posit that since the advent of technology, it has been identified as the basis for innovation through risk-taking and being proactive which results in an organization's better performance than competitors. Firms that focus on technological advancement through innovation research and development generate above average performance. For human resources to be unique and provide higher quality services for better performance than competitors, the firm must invest in its employees in terms of time and money through training and development and education (Lazear, 2009).

Demand forecasting, a function of resource management, allows managers to foresee the resource demand ahead of time. It enables them to assess and analyze the gaps within the existing capacity as well as mobilization of resources. After identifying the shortages and excesses, resource managers can formulate an action plan to proactively bridge the capacity vs demand gap. This measure, when effectively utilized and checked by senior management will address and minimize the instances of misappropriation, inaccuracies in records and supply shortages.

The potential success of any organization depends on its organizational performance, which means its ability to effectively implement strategies to achieve predetermined objectives or goals. (Randeree and Al Youha, 2009). The performance therefore is measured by the degree of achievement of its objectives, it significantly depends on the quality of its leadership and how well its strategy is formulated, Silva (2014). The business environment has become increasingly dynamic, driving companies to react with the same vigor to keep up for survival, making the necessary adaptations and changes. This race for market participation requires companies to closely monitor performance indicators so that it is possible to assess whether processes and activities are being performed satisfactorily to the point of using it as a competitive advantage, which has a major impact on the profitability of a firm, Neely (2007). To enable measurement of this performance, businesses are focused on creating performance indicators for each business area, which are designed and used in isolation. Thus, it is perceived that there is hardly any alignment between the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), and it is often possible that they could even be conflicting with each other (Neely 2007).

Every organization must have a strategy, organizational strategy can be defined as a systematic process by which organizational goals and objectives are to be achieved, it outlines the path towards achievement of the firm's goals. Organizational strategies are influenced by the feedback from the various organizational functions regarding the ability to provide the resources and inputs as well as produce the outcome necessary for those functions that contribute to the attainment of the goals and objectives of the organization as a whole. There are always challenges in the pursuit of success of an organization thus the leadership must have flexible plans that can adapt to the changes in the environment. For the organization's goals to be achieved through its strategy, the leadership must be able to communicate its plans to the employees effectively, (Tomal and Jones 2015). The knowledge and skill sets of its human capital is also a significant variable towards attainment of organization objectives, recruitment and selection of employees with the right set will result in high productivity and customer satisfaction which will ensure the sustainability of the organization (McLeod and Clarke 2011).

The concept of organizational performance can be very subjective and therefore, organizations may have different standards to measure performance, according to Cameron et al. (2014), stakeholders support the adaptability of their organizations; they need them to be flexible, stable, and effective. Because of the subjective nature of the definition of organizational performance, there is no general agreement by scholars on the standards to be used for its measurement (Neely 2015). However, an effective organization is a result of a high degree of collaboration and commitment among stakeholders through workgroups and management. The balanced scorecard is one approach of measuring performance and it includes not only financial measures with the result of actions already taken but also operational measures on customer satisfaction, organizational effectiveness, learning and growth that are the drivers of future financial performance (Kaplan and Norton, 2005). Organizations with better control over resources are likely to have the most influence on its performance (Scott, W. R., & Davis, 2015), and consequently, accomplishing objectives involves satisfying at least the minimal interests of all stakeholders. This study seeks to establish the relationship between the variables stakeholder involvement, resource availability, strategic risk management and knowledge and skills and organizational performance.

3. METHOD

The study adopted a descriptive research design with the target population of 89 management staff of the seed processing companies: Kenya Seed, Western Seed, ADC Seed Unit, Agri Seed, Bubayi Products and Zero Two Heroes. Due to small target population, the study worked with entire population which is census. Data collection instrument was structured questionnaire. Piloting was done to test validity and reliability of the research instrument. Completed questionnaires were checked for consistency, completeness and accuracy before being considered for analysis. Raw data was keyed in to a Microsoft Excel worksheet and into SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) version 26. The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics that is a linear regression model for the study.

4. DISCUSSION

Ismail et al (2012) examined the relationship between organizational resources, capabilities, systems and competitive advantage in terms of value and quantity and found that there is significant, positive effect of organizational resources, capabilities and systems collectively on competitive advantage. Barney (2007) claims that competitive advantage will lead to superior performance, given the fact that many firms focus their competitive strategy towards securing their resource pool. Additionally, Barney (2007) suggests that an organization's resources which may include capabilities, organizational processes, the firm's attributes, information and knowledge that is owned and controlled by the organization which will eventually enable the firm to conceive and implement strategies that will maximize its efficiency and effectiveness, giving it superior performance over its competitors. The study sought to identify the effect of resource availability on organizational performance in seed processing companies in Transzoia County, Kenya. The findings are presented in a five point likert scale where SA=strongly agree, A=agree, N=neutral, D=disagree, SD=strongly disagree and T=total.

From table 1 below, the respondents were asked whether the organization carry out regular budgeting and reviews in its strategic planning. The distribution of findings showed that 5.5 percent of the respondents strongly agreed, 35.5 percent of them agreed, 30.9 percent of the respondents were neutral, 11.8 percent disagreed while 16.4 percent of them strongly disagreed. These findings implied the organization carry out regular budgeting and reviews in its strategic planning.

The respondents were also asked whether resource availability is critical in driving the success of any organization. The distribution of the responses indicated that 6.4 percent strongly agreed to the statement, 36.4 percent of them agreed, 19.1 percent of them were neutral, 27.3 percent of them disagreed while 10.9 percent of them strongly disagreed to the statement. These findings implied majority of the respondents agreed that resource availability is critical in driving the success of any organization.

The respondents were also asked whether poor leadership in the utilization of resources is one of the main obstacles in successful strategy implementation, leading to failed organizations. The distribution of the responses indicated that 12.7 percent strongly agreed to the statement, 41.8 percent of them agreed, and 17.3 percent of them were neutral, 22.7 percent of them disagreed while 5.5 percent of them strongly disagreed to the statement. These findings implied that poor leadership in the utilization of resources is one of the main obstacles in successful strategy implementation, leading to failed organizations.

The respondents were further asked whether audit department for resource availability and allocation is vital proper planning. The distribution of the responses indicated that 0.9 percent strongly agreed to the statement, 52.7 percent of them agreed, 18.2 percent of them were neutral while 6.4 percent and 21.8 percent of them disagreed strongly and disagreed to the statement respectively. These findings implied that audit department for resource availability and allocation is vital proper planning.

The respondents were further asked whether organizational effectiveness has the proficiency which meet its objectives by meeting the planned outcome without waste or within minimum use of resources such as energy, finances, labor and time. The distribution of the responses indicated that 4.9 percent strongly agreed to the statement, 48.7 percent of them agreed, 15.3 percent of them were neutral while 12.5 percent and 19.6 percent of them disagreed strongly and disagreed to the statement respectively. These findings implied that organizational effectiveness has the proficiency which meets its objectives by achieving the planned outcome without waste or within minimum use of resources such as energy, finances, labor and time.

Table 1: Effect of Resource Availability on Organizational Performance in Seed Processing Companies in TransNzoia County, Kenya

Statements resource availability	SA	A	N	D	SD
The organization carry out regular budgeting and reviews in its strategic planning	% 5.5	35.5	30.9	11.8	16.4
Resource availability is critical in driving the success of any organization	% 6.4	36.4	19.1	27.3	10.9
Poor leadership in the utilization of resources is one of the main obstacles in successful strategy implementation, leading to failed organizations	% 12.7	41.8	17.3	22.7	5.5
Audit department for resource availability and allocation is vital for proper planning	% 0.9	52.7	18.2	6.4	21.8
Organizational effectiveness has the proficiency which meet its objectives by meeting the planned outcome without waste or within minimum use of resources such as energy, finances, labor and time	% 4.9	48.7	15.3	12.5	19.6

4.1 Inferential Statistics

4.1.1 Pearson Correlation

The study sought to establish the strength of the relationship between independent and dependent variables of the study. Pearson correlation coefficient was computed at 95 percent confidence interval (error margin of 0.05). Table 2 illustrates the findings of the study.

Table 2: Correlation Matrix

		Organizational performance
Resource availability	Pearson Correlation	.623**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000
	N	80

Findings from Table 2 above shows that the p-value for resource availability was found to be 0.000 which is less than the significant level of 0.05, ($p < 0.05$). The result indicated that Pearson Correlation coefficient (r-value) of 0.623, which represented a strong, positive relationship between resource availability on organizational performance in seed processing companies in TransNzoia County, Kenya.

4.1.2 Multiple Linear Regression

Multiple linear regressions were computed at 95 percent confidence interval (0.05 margin error) to show the multiple linear relationships between the independent and dependent variables of the study.

4.1.2.1 Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

Table 3 below shows that the coefficient of correlation (R) is positive 0.561. This means that there is a positive correlation between effects of strategic planning on the organizational performance of seed processing companies in TransNzoia County, Kenya. The coefficient of determination (R Square) indicates that 28.7% of organizational performance of seed processing companies in TransNzoia County, Kenya is influenced by the strategic planning. The adjusted R^2 however, indicates that 25.3% of organizational performance of seed processing companies in TransNzoia County, Kenya is influenced by the strategic planning leaving 74.7% to be influenced by other factors that were not captured in this study.

Table 3: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.561 ^a	.287	.253	9.20118

a. Predictors: (Constant), Resource Availability

4.1.2.2 Analysis of Variance

Table 4 shows the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The p-value is 0.000 which is < 0.05 indicates that the model is statistically significant in predicting how strategic planning affects organizational performance of seed processing companies in TransNzoia County, Kenya. The results also indicate that the independent variables are predictors of the dependent variable with an F test of 36.172.

Table 4: ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	617.032	4	237.311	36.172	.000 ^b
Residual	1476.232	76	15.964		
Total	2093.000	80			

4.1.2.3 Regression Coefficients

From the Coefficients table (Table 5) the regression model can be derived as follows:

$$Y = 49.031 + 0.769X_2$$

The results in table 5 indicate that all the independent variables have a significant positive effect on organizational performance of seed processing companies in TransNzoia County, Kenya. The influential variable is resource availability with a coefficient of 0.769 (p-value = 0.000). According to this model when the independent variable values are zero, organizational performance in seed processing companies in TransNzoia County, Kenya will have a score of 49.031.

Table 5: Regression Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	49.031	2.628		65.214	.000
	Resource availability	.769	.172	.735	5.443	.000

4.1.3 Hypothesis Testing

Ho₂: Resource availability does not have a significant effect on organizational performance in seed processing companies in TransNzoia County, Kenya.

From Table 5 above, resource availability ($\beta = 0.769$) was found to be positively related to organizational performance in seed processing companies in TransNzoia County, Kenya. From t-test analysis, the t-value was found to be 5.443 and the p-value 0.000. Statistically, this null hypothesis was rejected because $p < 0.05$. Thus, the study accepted the alternative hypothesis and it concluded that resource availability affects organizational performance in seed processing companies in TransNzoia County, Kenya.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In conclusion basing on the findings, resource availability ($\beta = 0.792$) was found to be positively related to organizational performance in seed processing companies in TransNzoia county, Kenya. From t-test analysis, the t-value was found to be 5.442 and the p-value 0.000. Statistically, this null hypothesis was rejected because $p < 0.05$. Thus, the study accepted the alternative hypothesis and it concluded that resource availability affects organizational performance in seed processing companies in TransNzoia County, Kenya.

The study recommends that the management of seed companies should ensure that regular budgeting and reviews in its strategic planning and that resource availability, outcome waste or within minimum use of resources such as energy, finances, labor and time critically in driving the success of any organization. The management of seed companies should come up with regular training programs to equip employees with latest skills, knowledge, and abilities, with the aim of building organizational capabilities and improving organizational performance.

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